

A New Synthesis of 4-Alkyl and 3,4-Dialkyl Isocoumarins

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4-Ethylisochroman (Va) and 3,4-diethylisochroman (Vb) on oxidation furnish 4-ethyl and 3,4-diethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (VIa and VIb). Treatment of these compounds with N-bromosuccinimide followed by refluxing with triethylamine furnishes 4-ethyl and 3,4-diethylisocoumarins (VIIa and VIIb). Va and Vb were obtained by treating 2-phenylbutan-1-ol (IVa) and 4-phenylhexan-3-ol (IVb) with HCHO/HCl, respectively. IVa is obtained from α -phenylbutyraldehyde (III) by reduction whereas IVb is obtained from III by Grignard reaction with ethyl magnesium iodide. The aldehyde (III) is obtained from propiophenone (I) by Darzen's glycidic ester condensation followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation of the resulting product.

DESAI and Usgaonkar¹ obtained 4-methylisocoumarins by the cyclodehydration of acetyl esters of appropriately substituted benzoic acids and 3,4-dimethylisocoumarins^{2,3} by cyclodehydration of α -methyl acetyl esters of benzoic acids in presence of 85% H₂SO₄. The acetyl esters however undergo hydrolysis during cyclodehydration. The hydrolysis competes with cyclodehydration, thereby affecting considerably the yield of isocoumarins. We report a new route by which the synthesis of 4-ethylisocoumarin and 3,4-diethylisocoumarin is accomplished by us. It has the potentiality of being developed as a general route for the synthesis of 4-alkylisocoumarins and 3,4-dialkylisocoumarins.

Propiophenone (I) was converted into α -phenylbutyraldehyde (III) via ethyl β -ethyl- β -phenylglycidate (II). The ester was obtained from I by Darzen's glycidic ester condensation, hydrolysed and then decarboxylated to give III. The aldehyde (III) on reduction with sodium borohydride or aluminium isopropoxide furnished 2-phenylbutan-1-ol (IVa). Treatment of aldehyde (III) with ethyl magnesium iodide furnished 4-phenylhexan-3-ol (IVb). IVa and IVb were converted into 4-ethylisochroman (Va) and 3,4-diethylisochroman (Vb), respectively by passing hydrogen chloride gas through a solution of the compound and formalin (37%) in dry dioxane. Oxidation of Va and Vb by chromium trioxide in glacial acetic acid or by selenium dioxide in boiling xylene furnished 4-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIa) and 3,4-diethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIb), respectively. VIa furnished 4-ethylisocoumarin (VIIa) on treatment with NBS in boiling carbon tetrachloride in the presence of a 60 watt lamp followed by refluxing the 4-bromo derivative obtained after removal of the solvent with triethylamine for a prolonged period. In the conversion of VIb into 3,4-diethylisocoumarin (VIIb), elimination of hydrogen bromide from the 4-bromoderivative formed by the action with NBS took place partially during the removal of the

solvent. The reaction was completed by refluxing the same with triethylamine for a prolonged period.

1. ClCH₂COOEt, 2. $\bar{O}Et$, 3. aq NaOH or NaOEt-H₂O,
4. a; NaBH₄ or Al-isopropoxide, 5. HCHO/HCl,
- b; EtMgI,
6. CrO₃ or SeO₂,
7. NBS-Et₃N.,
a; R=H
b; R=C₂H₅

Experimental

Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. UV spectra were recorded on Beckmann model DK-2A spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elemer, model 577 spectrophotometer. 60 MHz pmr spectra were recorded on Varian A60 instrument with TMS as an internal standard.

Ethyl β -ethyl- β -phenyl glycidate(II): To a mixture of dry propiophenone (33.0 ml) and dry ethyl chloroacetate (25.0 ml) in dry benzene (50 ml), sodium ethoxide solution in ethanol (5.75 g sodium in 100 ml absolute ethanol) was added dropwise at 15°. After stirring the mixture for 2 hr at room temp., it was poured on crushed ice. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with benzene (2 \times 50 ml). The organic layer and the benzene extracts were mixed, washed with water (2 \times 75 ml) and dil. acetic acid (2.5 ml in 75 ml water) and then dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent, the liquid residue was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 145-50°/3 mm, yield 44 g. (Found: C, 77.01; H, 7.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8$; C, 77.18; H, 7.31%). IR (neat): 3060, 3030, 2980, 2940, (C-H), 1740 (C=O of ester), 1600, 1580, 1495, 1415 (aromatic) 1380 and 1225 cm^{-1} .

α -Phenylbutyraldehyde (III):

(i) Ethyl β -ethyl- β -phenyl glycidate (30 g) was added to a stirred solution of sodium hydroxide (12 g) in water (30 ml) when a solid started separating after 10 min. Stirring was continued for 2 hr at 50-60° resulting in a clear homogeneous liquid which on cooling solidified, acidified to congo red with hydrochloric acid (6*N*), heated for 1 hr on water bath with the evolution of carbon dioxide and finally separation of an oil. After cooling, the oil was extracted with benzene (2 \times 20 ml), the combined benzene extract washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave a residue which was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 84°/3 mm, yield 13.2 g. (Found: C, 80.71; H, 8.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$; C, 81.04; H, 8.16%). IR (neat): 3060, 3020, 2940, 2840, 1720, 1605, 1580, 1450, 1410 and 1350 cm^{-1} .

(ii) To a solution of sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (2 g) and absolute alcohol (40 ml) was added II (18 g) slowly with stirring. After cooling the reaction mixture externally to 15°, water (2 ml) was added slowly when a sodium salt separated. It was kept overnight and the salt filtered, washed with absolute ethanol (6 ml) and then ether (6 ml). It was then refluxed with hydrochloric acid (50 ml; 2*N*) for 1.5 hr, when carbon dioxide was evolved with the separation of an oil. The oil was extracted with benzene (2 \times 25 ml) and the benzene extract washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave an oil which distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 78°/2 mm.

2-Phenylbutan-1-ol (IVa):

(i) To a solution of aluminium isopropoxide from aluminium (1.095 g), mercuric chloride (0.03 g) and dry isopropylalcohol (12 ml), 2-phenylbutyraldehyde (10.8 g) in dry isopropyl alcohol (40 ml) was added and the mixture heated in oil bath at 110° for 6 hr with an efficient fractionating column and an arrangement for distillation to distill acetone as it is formed. The temp. of the top of the fractionating column was maintained at 60-70°. When no more of acetone distilled, the reaction was stopped and isopropyl alcohol in the mixture was removed under

reduced pressure. The residue on cooling was hydrolysed by keeping with cold dil. hydrochloric acid for 6 hr. It was then extracted with benzene (3 \times 25 ml) and the benzene extract after washing with water was dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave an oil. It was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 110°/4 mm, yield 8 ml. (Found: C, 79.84; H, 9.21. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$; C, 79.95; H, 9.39%). IR (neat): 3400 (OH), 3080, 3060, 3025, 2960, 2800, 1600, 1450 and 1378 cm^{-1} .

(ii) 2-Phenylbutyraldehyde (8.2 g) in ethanol (50 ml) and sodium hydroxide (100 ml; 10%) was treated with sodium borohydride (4.5 g) in small portions. After the addition was over the reaction mixture was kept overnight and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. Most of the ethanol was removed by distillation on a water bath and the residue diluted with water (100 ml) and extracted with ether (3 \times 30 ml). The ether extract was washed with water and dried (MgSO_4). Removal of the solvent gave an oil. It was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish (IVa) (7.5 g), b.p. 109-10°/4 mm, identical with the previous specimen by elemental analyses, b.p. and ir spectra.

4-Ethylisochroman (Va): Dry hydrogen chloride gas was bubbled in a solution of IVa (7 g), formalin (7.5 ml; 37%) and conc. hydrochloric acid (3 ml) in dry dioxane (10 ml) for 2 hr at such a rate that temp. of the mixture remained in the range of 50-60°. After cooling it was poured into ice water and extracted with ether (3 \times 40 ml). The ether extract was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate, water and dried (fused CaCl_2). After removal of the solvent, the residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish Va (6.3 g) as a colourless liquid, b.p. 88°/4 mm. (Found: C, 81.32; H, 8.23. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$; C, 81.43; H, 8.69%). UV (EtOH): 272 nm. IR (neat): 3090, 3060, 2950, 1450, 1380, 1105 (ethereal) and 1610 cm^{-1} . PMR(CCl_4): δ 0.93 (3H, *m*, $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.8-2.0 (2H, *m*, $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.65 (2H, *m*, H-1); 4.10 (2H, *m*, H-3), 3.66 (1H, *m*, H-4), 7.3 (4H, *m*, aromatic).

4-Ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIa):

(i) A solution of chromium trioxide (6 g) in water (9 ml) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of Va (3 g) in glacial acetic acid (60 ml) at room temp. The reaction was exothermic and it was cooled occasionally by ice to maintain the temperature at 30-35°. It was stirred for 2 hr at room temp., then mixed with an equal volume of water and was extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (10%), water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave an oil which was distilled under reduced pressure as brown liquid, b.p. 144-46°/1 mm, yield 2.5 g. (Found C, 74.72; H, 6.81. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$; C, 74.97; H, 6.87%). UV (EtOH): 250 and 280 nm. IR (neat): 3090, 3065, 2945, 1730 (C=O of lactone), 1610 (aromatic), 1450 and 1380 cm^{-1} . PMR(CCl_4): δ 0.91 (3H, *t*, $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.50-2.15 (2H, *m*, $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.72 (2H, *m*, H-3), 3.67 (1H, *m*, H-4), 8.10 (1H, *s*, H-8), 7.30 (3H, *m*, aromatic).

(ii) A solution of Va (2 g) in xylene (25 ml) was treated with freshly prepared selenium dioxide (1.6 g) and refluxed for 6 hr. The hot reaction mixture was filtered and the residue obtained after removal of the solvent was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over neutral alumina (40 g), eluting the column with the same solvent. The clear liquid that was obtained after removing the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 152-53°/2.5 mm, yield 1.4 g. It was identified with the above specimen by uv and ir.

4-Ethylisocoumarin (VIIa): A mixture of VIa (3g), N-bromosuccinimide (3 g) and benzoyl peroxide (0.05 g) in dry carbon tetrachloride (40 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr, the reaction flask being kept close to a 60 watt lamp. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the filtrate washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%), water and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed on water bath. The residue was refluxed with triethylamine (50 ml) for 6 hr and the gummy residue left after removal of triethylamine was triturated repeatedly with ice cold hydrochloric acid (2N) followed by water. It was then taken in carbon tetrachloride, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 172-74°/2 mm, yield 1.6 g. (Found: C, 75.49; H, 5.61 Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₀O₂; C, 75.84; H, 5.78%). UV (EtOH): 280 and 325 nm; IR (neat): 3095, 3065, 2942, 1742 (C=O of lactone), 1600, 1580, 1450 and 1380 cm⁻¹. PMR(CCl₄): δ 0.9 (3H, t, C₄-CH₂CH₃), 3.1 (2H, q, C₄-CH₂CH₃), 7.3 (1H, s, H-3), 8.1 (1H, m, H-8), 7.2 (3H, m, aromatic).

4-Phenylhexan-3-ol (IVb): 2-Phenylbutanal (III, 9 g) in dry ether (20 ml) was added to the Grignard solution, prepared from magnesium (2 g) and ethyl iodide (10 g) in dry ether (20 ml) with stirring and was refluxed for 1 hr. The ethereal solution was poured onto crushed ice, acidified with dil. sulphuric acid and extracted with ether (2 × 20 ml). The ether extract was washed with dil. sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried (anhydrous K₂CO₃). The solvent was removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 96-7°/1.5 mm, yield 10 g. On redistillation, the liquid distilled at 104°/2.5 mm to yield IVb (8.5 g). (Found: C, 80.44; H, 9.83. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₈O; C, 80.84; H, 10.17%). IR (neat): 3445 (OH), 3080, 3040, 3027, 2985, 2940, 2880 (C-H), 1600, 1452 (aromatic) and 1380 cm⁻¹.

3,4-Diethylisochroman (Vb): The reaction was carried out as under Va by passing dry hydrogen chloride gas into a solution of IVb (3 g), formalin (3-4 ml; 37%), conc. hydrochloric acid (1.5 ml) in pure and dry dioxane (9 ml) and was worked in the same manner. The product distilled under reduced pressure as colourless liquid, b.p. 85°/1 mm, yield 2.4 g. (Found: C, 82.16; H, 9.12. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₈O; C, 82.05; H, 9.4%). UV(EtOH): 240 and 245 nm; IR (neat): 3060, 3000, 2950 (C-H), 1600, 1480 (aromatic), 1400 and 1100 (etheral) cm⁻¹. PMR(CCl₄): δ 0.91 (6H, m, C₃-CH₂CH₃ and C₄-CH₂CH₃), 1.45-2.15 (4H, m, C₃-CH₂CH₃ and C₄-CH₂CH₃), 2.50 (1H, m, H-3), 3.66 (1H, m, H-4), 4.75 (2H, q, H-1), 7.20 (4H, m, aromatic).

3,4-Diethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIb): Oxidation of Vb by the methods (i) or (ii) as in the case of VIa furnished VIb as a brownish yellow liquid, b.p. 155-58°/2 mm, yield 78%. (Found: C, 76.17; H, 7.35. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₆O₂; C, 76.43; H, 7.85%). UV(EtOH): 250 and 290 nm. IR (neat): 3100, 3010, 2940 (C-H), 1730 (C=O of lactone), 1620, 1480 (aromatic) and 1400 cm⁻¹. PMR(CCl₄): δ 0.92 (6H, t, C₃-CH₂CH₃ and C₄-CH₂CH₃), 1.55-2.00 (4H, m, C₃-CH₂CH₃ and C₄-CH₂CH₃), 2.75 (1H, m, H-3), 4.46 (1H, m, H-4), 8.26 (1H, m, H-8), 7.41 (3H, m, aromatic).

3,4-Diethylisocoumarin (VIIb): The reaction was carried and worked up as under VIIa using a mixture of VIb (2 g), N-bromosuccinimide (2.1 g), benzoyl peroxide (0.03 g) and dry carbon tetrachloride (20 ml) with a 60 watt lamp. During the removal of the solvent on boiling water bath, evolution of hydrogen bromide was observed. The residue in the flask was further refluxed with triethylamine (50 ml) as before. The product crystallised from ethyl acetate-ether (60-80°) as needles, m.p. 144-45°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 77.71; H, 6.92. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄O; C, 77.75; H, 6.97%). UV(EtOH): 240, 280, 325 nm. IR(KBr): 3100, 3005, 2945 (C-H), 1740 (C=O of lactone), 1630, 1620, 1480 and 1400 cm⁻¹ (aromatic). PMR(CCl₄): δ 0.96 (6H, t, C₃-CH₂CH₃ and C₄-CH₂CH₃), 2.60-3.15 (4H, m, C₃-CH₂CH₃ and C₄-CH₂CH₃), 8.30 (1H, m, H-8), 7.60 (3H, m, aromatic).

References

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